

Commentary for *Vaccine*

Publication of Prespecified Outcomes in Bandim Health Project Trials: A Response to Støvring et al

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Publication of Prespecified Outcomes in Bandim Health Project Trials: A Response to Støvring et al

We read with interest the commentary by Støvring et al.[1], which examines randomized controlled trials (RCTs) conducted by the Bandim Health Project (BHP) and raises concerns regarding the publication of prespecified outcomes. The authors report having reviewed 38 trials and identify 10 for which they state that one or more prespecified primary outcomes were not published. We have reassessed these claims against the published literature and trial records and find that they are not supported by the available evidence.

Historical context of trial registration

In 2004-2005, major medical journals, coordinated through the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors, announced that trial registration would be required for publication. At that time, there was uncertainty as to whether this requirement applied only prospectively or also to trials already underway or completed. In light of the uncertainty, and in good faith, BHP registered a large group of trials in September 2005, that had been initiated or completed before registration.

Seven of the 10 trials highlighted by Støvring et al. fall into this category. The trials were initiated between 1995 and 2004. They had received scientific and ethical approval from relevant authorities.

In 2005, ClinicalTrials.gov did not require structured specification of primary and secondary outcomes and trial protocols did not consistently distinguish between primary and secondary outcomes in the manner now required. During the retrospective registration in 2005, outcome descriptions were often brief and/or narrative. In some cases, they included aspirational outcomes, contingent on future funding. Registry entries were substantially less detailed than approved protocols and were not treated as the governing study document, which were the approved protocols.

It was not until December 2007 that ClinicalTrials.gov introduced mandatory, structured primary and secondary outcome fields. Under such standards, the trials would have designated mortality as the sole primary outcome, with other endpoints classified as secondary.

The authors' retrospective application of later registry standards to these early registrations is therefore methodologically inappropriate. Crucially, mortality outcomes have been published for all completed trials discussed by Støvring et al. The allegation that primary outcomes were not published therefore rests on a reinterpretation of early registry entries rather than on evidence of selective non-publication.

Prospectively registered trials

Three of the 10 trials were initiated after September 2005 and were therefore prospectively registered. Two of these were initiated in 2005 and 2007, respectively. For both trials, all outcomes specified in the registry have been published (Table). These publications were not acknowledged by Støvring et al. These omissions materially affect their conclusions.

The remaining trial (NCT04383925) is a COVID-era study. Publication of its primary outcome has been delayed due to disruptions caused by the pandemic. A manuscript is currently in preparation. This is the only prospectively registered trial identified by the authors for which results are not yet published.

Findings across all 38 RCTs

Most importantly, despite reviewing all 38 RCTs conducted by BHP, the authors identify no completed trial that was prospectively registered prior to initiation and subsequently failed to publish its prespecified primary outcomes. This holds across all trials included in their review. The only exception cited is the ongoing COVID-delayed study noted above.

Thus, rather than documenting selective non-publication, the authors' own analysis demonstrates that BHP has adhered to prospective registration and outcome reporting requirements once these were clearly established.

Conclusion

In summary:

- Seven trials were retrospectively registered in 2005 under early registry standards.
- Two prospectively registered trials registered before December 2007 published the outcomes specified in the trial registry.
- One prospectively registered trial initiated in 2020 remains unpublished due to COVID-related delays.
- Across all completed prospectively registered trials, no instance of non-publication of primary outcomes was identified.

Accordingly, the allegation that BHP failed to publish prespecified primary outcomes is not supported by the published record. These discrepancies concern verifiable statements about the publication status of prespecified outcomes and therefore constitute factual inaccuracies that directly affect the interpretation of the article's conclusions.

Table. Three prospectively registered randomized controlled trials identified by Støvring et al. as allegedly not having published one or more prespecified primary outcomes.

	Study	First registered at ClinicalTrials.gov	Study start	Claim from Støvring et al	Clarifications and publications
NCT04383925	Comparing two BCG strains	May 2020	September 2020	Did not report primary outcomes	Manuscript in preparation, delayed due to COVID19.
NCT00244673	The effect of receiving DTP vaccine with or after measles vaccine	October 2005	October 2005	Did not report mortality (for DTP3); Hospitalizations; Adverse events	Mortality for DTP3, hospitalizations and adverse events reported in Agergaard et al 2011[2] and Agergaard et al 2025[3].
NCT00514891	Vitamin A at immunization contacts	August 2007	August 2007	Did not report morbidity	Morbidity reported in Fisker et al 2013[4].

References

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